

A Highly Refined Explanation Model for Life Phenomena through Interdisciplinary Theoretical Exploration

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Life phenomena are described as non-equilibrium processes that proceed by extracting entropy through self-organization. Fluctuations and renormalization are important concepts in life phenomena. It is important to note the functionality of explaining life phenomena. The process of adaptive evolution of life phenomena can be explained in principle from many points of view. In general, life phenomena are contextual, relative, and dynamic systems that change continuously. To describe this, we used novel concepts of support and selective pressure, organizing and being organized, ambivalence, adaptive spatiotemporal paths, and exploration and request. In this study, we attempt to provide a progressive model explaining universal mechanisms in life phenomena that allows us to describe the principles that govern the autonomy, cooperativity, and evolvability of living systems in more detail. We describe a novel mechanism to explain the relative nature of the dissipative principle responsible for extracting entropy in living systems. Description of a more progressive mechanism for the cooperative evolutionary process of renormalization, dissipative principles, and functional evolution. By explaining new mechanisms, principles, and relationships between micro and macro, entropy, fluctuations, dissipative principles, renormalization, adaptive spatiotemporal paths, and other abstractive concepts, we deepen the universal explanation model of the autonomous, cooperative, and evolutionary dynamics of life phenomena and provide a progressive view of the evolutionary process. The objective of this paper is to provide a progressive view of the dynamics of autonomous, cooperative, and evolutionary life phenomena by explaining novel mechanisms, principles, and associations and to suggest possibilities for further research.

Life phenomenon is through the real and imaginary fluctuation of the ambivalence of possibility and impossibility in a vertical direction against the surface of space-time, to be as a functional system dissipating by deepening relative dissipative structures in deepening the dimensional sum of products of entropy.

Thereby, it is generated the cooperative system of renormalizing relative dissipative structures to organize the fluctuation of ambivalence of thermodynamic entropy and information entropy in space-time and the ambivalence of extracting entropy by organizing and being organized in relation to relative dissipative structures along spatiotemporal paths formed by interaction in space-time.

It explores for and is requested concerning the emergence that releases the contradiction, which is considered as a new dimension by internal and external renormalization through interactions of ambivalence of possibility and impossibility in space-time in organizing and being organized through competition and cooperation with entropy by deepening functional, stable and sustainable dissipative structures, deepening functionality, braiding up and defusing the freedom and constraints through the ambivalence of support and selective pressure, deepening the ability to organize them, in the fluctuation of relative functionality. It explores for and is requested of in terms of renormalization of dissipative structures in space-time, and be organized by the dynamics of relative gradient contours of spatiotemporal dissipation, to make internal and external relative dissipative structures cooperate through renormalization by organizing and being organized through relative adaptability of functionality, stability and the ability of organization

Then, it forms co-evolving process of relative fluctuation of ambivalence of support and selective pressure of functionality, entropy and space-time to learn, maintain and predict each other through orientation and demand along spatiotemporal paths through adaptive evolution to explore for and requested from the internal and external edge of chaos to edge of chaos, to be organizing and being organized concerning the ability of analysis and abstraction of space-time by relative dissipative structures.

Owing to the nature of creating value in space-time, it is organized and organizing along spatiotemporal paths, renormalized to the other dissipative structure and renormalizing the other dissipative structure to it, formed by the dissipation through the deepening and organizing of dissipative structures and through renormalization and dissipation of them, to be formed, deepened and organized as dissipative structures with higher order.

Thus, life phenomena can be considered as a complex cooperating system renormalized and dissipating by organizing and being organized in terms of its fluctuation of relative adaptability in space-time to explore for and requested from the functionality in the process of organizing and being organized in terms of non-equilibrium process to deepen the

dissipative structure to be relatively adaptive in space-time.

In this study, space-time is represented as a single system of space and time, however its uniformity is assumed to be dynamic, with variations, distortions, and fluctuations due to the relativity of life phenomena, entropy, and value.

The dissipative structure is a concept proposed by Ilya Prigogine, which is a structure that dissipates free energy through self-organization in non-equilibrium open systems and partially reducing the entropy of the system and bringing order to the whole system.

In addition, there is a part that uses the word "dissipate" to mean to dissipate by discarding. The word "renormalization" is cited from the description of life phenomena explained by non-linear dynamics [Y, Ohno], however more broadly, it can be thought of as a flow into, entrainment of, or compromise turnaround of a system of action.

Fluctuation represents the dynamics of non-linear spatiotemporal changes in the probability distribution of the system.

Organizing and being organized refer to the formation and movement of hierarchical organizational structures, active or passive, that generate new, cooperatively functioning, dynamic systems on a larger scale.

The edge of chaos refers to the cooperative and creative state generated by the emergence of chaos through self-organization.

Such a system maintains adaptability through competition and cooperation, self-protection, the dissipative principle, and feedback in exploring for sustainability.

First, the idea of understanding the relative fluctuations of dissipative structure and spatiotemporal entropy as a probability density gradient model of dissipative structure, space-time and competition and cooperation was derived from the statistical mechanics description of fluctuations and entropy.

Through the idea of energy level that chemical reactions proceed in such a way that the products became more stable in theoretical chemistry, and the model of flow into the center by probability density gradient, and the three-dimensional organizational structure model, we obtained the idea of describing the dissipative structure model as a three-dimensional entropy flow gradient model.

I also thought about the mechanism of dissipation as a mechanism beyond renormalization, and I deepened the theory by considering the supporting mechanism.

I thought about the relation between normal distribution curves and wave curves because I naturally imaged them in terms of the concept of fluctuation.

Furthermore, the wave curve seemed to express the homeostasis and internal structure of the life phenomena.

To describe the nature of the relativity of dissipative structure extracting entropy in space-time, it would probably be useful understanding the mechanism through the analogy of the fish swimming in the sea, which is exploring for the safe space, stay for a while and leave out again in the fluctuation in the environment.

The double helix structure of DNA represents many mechanisms of life, such as reversal and renormalization of support and selective pressure, and organization of ambivalence.

Furthermore, its non-linear and gradual behavior in three-dimensional space and the asymmetric separation of information are not unrelated to the law of physics.

Consideration

coordination of functionality that bring about relative adaptability in space-time. From a quantum mechanical point of view, the average stochastic process is adaptively organized by the coordination of internal and external dissipative structures and analyze spatiotemporal fluctuations as they dissipate. Up to this point, I had somehow imagined the one of interpretations in systems biology that life phenomena could be analogous to black holes.

However, let us consider the concept of adaptive organization of ambivalence and dynamic equilibrium in terms of quantum mechanics. It is the concept of conjugated systems in organic chemistry. Conjugated systems are systems in which reactants in unstable states are energetically stabilized by conjugation. The conjugated system is generated by the energetic stabilization of reactants in unstable states through conjugation. It can be regarded as a kind of dissipative structure.

In other words, can we explain life phenomena as a conjugated system of entropy fluctuation and space-time fluctuation?

By using quantum mechanics, relativity and topological geometry, it can be explained as a Kleinian vase-like confinement system generated as a conjugated system of entropy fluctuation and space-time fluctuation. It seems to clearly express the mechanism of self-organization of life phenomena and is suggestive of the possibility of explanation by many principles and mechanisms.

If we were to extract three models that characterize these concepts, they would be the normal distribution, the 8-figure loop, and the converging overlapped spiral. It is an effective model for describing entropy and space-time fluctuations, as well as for describing the dynamics of their relativity and interaction. It would describe the boundary, cooperative, and relative nature of life phenomena by their ability to separate and combine these structures; it would describe the dynamic equilibrium nature of the divergence and cohesion of fluctuations; and it would describe the self-protective gradualism by describing the recursive cycle of non-linearities.

From these considerations life can be described as a deepening process of autonomously evolving relative dissipative structures, generated by the recursive circulation of the internal and external continuous renormalization of the relative fluctuations of informational fluctuations and free energy inflow and their dissipation, which are continuously produced by the twisting and resolution of space-time.

It is interesting that the dynamics of double helix structure presents such a mechanism, and it is probably not on mere coincidence.

It is the relative fluctuations of space-time and entropy that are renormalized for relative

adaptability by the 0-ness and ∞ -ness of the edge of chaos, generated in the balance between destruction and creation.

It is a cyclical system in which the relative fluctuations of space-time and entropy recurse as they are renormalized for relative adaptability.

In other words, in the process of 0 exploring for ∞ , and ∞ exploring for 0, it finds its proximity to the edge of chaos and becomes stuck.

It could be thought of as a highly renormalized gradualism as the gradient or differential coefficient of the process between 0 and ∞ .

The living system can be described as differential equation with gradual renormalization of the cooperation between entropy and space-time, which is cyclically regresses to be adaptive by the fluctuation of relativity due to boundedness in the edge of chaos with a spherical structure.

This explanation model provides the simplicity and the polysemy to the way of understanding through its mechanism. These qualities are thought to facilitate cross-disciplinary discussion, enhance understanding from many fields, and contribute to the creation, deepening and sophistication of new academic disciplines.

Field area.

Interdisciplinary Research for New Explanation Model for Life Phenomena

Overlap area.

entropy, dissipative structure, space-time, nonlinear dynamics, renormalization

Related area.

statistics, fluctuation, complex system, topological geometry, physical chemistry

Quality.

dimension, coordinate axis, asymmetry, gradualism, boundary

Emergent related items.

contradiction, relativity, ambivalence, internal and external, 0 and ∞ , adaptability, edge of chaos

orbit, cycle, balance, equilibrium, stable phase

dimension, branch, symmetry, analysis, path selection

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10.5281/zenodo.12732503.

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